

Report to Congress

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's Report on Inventory of Space Weather Data for Operational Forecasting and Potential and Existing Gaps

For the Senate Committee on Appropriations
as Requested in Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2016
Senate Report 114-66

August 2017

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) prepared this document in response to both the Senate Report 114-66, and the House Explanatory Statement which accompanied the Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2016 (P.L. 114-113). The House Explanatory Statement provided the following direction:

Senate language regarding a report on initial findings is adopted by reference and shall be submitted to the Committees no more than one year after enactment of this Act. This report shall include an inventory of all existing and planned space weather assets held by NOAA and NOAA's partners, to include each asset's function, operation and maintenance expenses, and lifetime cost estimates, and shall identify any potential gaps in data needed for space weather forecasting.

Senate Report 114-66 provided the following direction:

NOAA is directed to submit a report to the Committee detailing: space weather data needs for operational forecasting, various options for attaining such data, cost estimates for those options, and corresponding timelines. The report shall also analyze the potential impact of a space weather data gap after 2019.

This report contains an introduction to space weather, a discussion of customer needs for geomagnetic storm forecasting (Section II), a discussion of observations and products used for geomagnetic storm forecasting (Section III), known and potential gaps in forecasting (Section IV), and a complete inventory of all existing and planned space weather assets held by NOAA and NOAA's partners (Section V).

Section I: Introduction

Space weather is a branch of space physics and aeronomy concerned with varying phenomena within the solar system and how those phenomena impact the space surrounding the Earth, including conditions in the magnetosphere, ionosphere, and thermosphere. Space weather poses a significant threat to our economic vitality and national security, as it impacts integrated technological systems upon which the global economy fully depends. Space weather impacts spacecraft such as satellites, human space exploration, power grids, and radio communications

that support global positioning systems, airlines, pipelines, and railway systems, among many others.

Space weather is driven by a variety of solar phenomena such as solar flares, coronal mass ejections (CMEs), high-speed solar wind, and relativistic proton events.¹ Each of these drive different types of space weather toward Earth and are observed and measured by a variety of products and services issued by NOAA's National Weather Service (NWS) Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC). SWPC operates 24 hours a day every day of the year to support customers that keep our Nation's power grid, airlines, satellites, and navigation systems safe and functional.

There are three major types of space weather events: radio blackout, solar radiation storms, and geomagnetic storms. Geomagnetic storms – initiated by CMEs and high-speed solar wind – can cause major disturbances in Earth's magnetosphere and disrupt power systems, spacecraft operations, and navigation systems. The forecasting of geomagnetic storms has been identified as the highest priority to the Nation.

While SWPC observes other space weather events, this report will focus solely on assets and data needs related to the forecasting of geomagnetic storms because of their over-sized impact on technology and the economy. NOAA identifies, documents, and prioritizes observation requirements consistent with rigorous protocols and in support of the needs of space weather customers, as discussed in Section II.

Process Overview for Identifying Geomagnetic Storms

The NOAA Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites (GOES) are used to identify coronal holes, which are the source of high speed solar wind. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) / European Space Agency (ESA) Solar and Heliospheric Observatory's Large Angle Spectrometric Coronagraph (SOHO/LASCO) is used to identify CMEs that have erupted and whether they are directed at Earth. After a CME leaves the field of view of SOHO, there is then no opportunity to learn or observe anything more until the solar wind or CME are sampled directly by a spacecraft. These measurements are made possible by, for example, the Deep Space Climate Observatory (DSCOVR), which is located in the solar wind at a point upstream from the Earth, providing up to one hour of advance warning. When significant conditions are measured with DSCOVR, SWPC is able to issue a highly accurate Geomagnetic Storm Warning to customers. A geomagnetic storm can last from a few hours to as long as several days with changing intensity throughout. During the event, SWPC uses DSCOVR data to continually provide customers with updated warnings.

During a geomagnetic storm, the impact is affected by fluctuations in the Earth's magnetic field. These fluctuations, and thus the intensity of the storm, are measured with ground based magnetometers. SWPC uses the USGS ground based observations to issue Geomagnetic Storm Alerts to customers for the duration of the geomagnetic storm.

¹ Space Weather Phenomena: www.swpc.noaa.gov/phenomena

With these and other data, SWPC is able to provide customers with forecasts of geomagnetic storms and issue the earliest possible Geomagnetic Storm Watch products. SWPC provides geomagnetic storm watches, warnings, and alerts to customers using the Geomagnetic Storm Scale, measuring storms on a scale from 1 (minor) to 5 (extreme).

Section II: Customer Needs for Geomagnetic Storm Forecasts

SWPC uses gathered customer needs to inform observing system requirements, which are codified and prioritized in the NOAA Consolidated Observing User Requirements List (COURL). SWPC meets customer needs through forecasts, watches, and warnings, providing real-time situational awareness of impacts to their systems. In this section, we limit the customer needs discussion to only those that relate to geomagnetic storm forecasts (as discussed in Section I). The discussion below is not intended as a complete description of customer needs for space weather.

Electric Power

The risks to the Nation from space weather impacts on the electric power grid are extreme and the reason this report focuses on forecasting geomagnetic storms. This risk has been identified in the *Strategic National Risk Assessment in Support of Presidential Policy Directive 8 (PPD-8): National Preparedness*. PPD-8 is aimed at strengthening the security and resilience of the United States through systematic preparation for the threats that pose the greatest risk to the security of the Nation, and identifies space weather as a National Level Event.

SWPC works closely with power grid operators and power companies to identify space weather-related requirements (the most stringent across all industries) and develop appropriate products and services. Power grid impacts from space weather are almost entirely related to geomagnetic storms and an extreme event can erupt from the sun and impact Earth in less than one day. With a required warning lead sometimes as short as five minutes, meeting the needs of power grids operators can challenge our current forecast capabilities.

With longer lead-time (1-3 days) notifications of a storm, transmission operators can assess the readiness of spare offline generators and can notify field personnel of the potential need to report to individual substations for on-site monitoring. In addition, safe-system posturing is possible by putting offline equipment online and by delaying planned outages.

For lead times that are a few hours, system operators can monitor more closely for the reactive reserve (making the system less vulnerable to a collapse), monitor for unusual voltage or reactive power swings, monitor transformers for abnormal temperature, noise, or dissolved gas, and monitor directly for induced currents if they have the capability. This lead time also enables operators to prepare for unplanned capacitor bank and/or static-var-compensator tripping. Operators can also assume a more conservative posture by starting off-line generation and by reducing transfer limits.

For the shortest lead times (30 minutes) and also in response to real-time information, operators may also carry out selective load shedding (drop service to certain customers) and/or manually start fans or pumps to improve cooling of selected transformers. Furthermore, depending on previous analyses, operators may be advised to remove certain transformers from service if imminent damage is anticipated, may be advised to remove selected transmission lines from service, or may carry out system reconfiguration.

What power companies need in addition to the watches and warnings are spatially resolved forecasts as well as predictions of the geo-electric field at their operating site. Systems engineers in particular have asked for six hour or more forecasts, updated hourly, of the geo-electric field, which is calculated from the geomagnetic field forecast and informs grid operators of the impact on their systems.

Global Positioning/Navigation Services

Precise positioning and navigation is critical global commerce, mining, drilling, and surveying for a broad range of industries. Position and navigation accuracy also is vital for a variety of military and national security needs. In terms of geomagnetic storm forecasting value, forecasts more than one hour in advance up to a few days in advance are needed. Forecasts enable users to postpone or modify operations to avoid periods where the positioning does not meet the necessary accuracy. Shorter lead-time warnings are also useful for avoiding survey work that could result in poor quality data.

Aviation

Geomagnetic storms affect global positioning/navigation services and communications systems on aircraft. Geomagnetic storms can also modulate the ability of ionizing radiation to enter deeply into the atmosphere, creating a risk of radiation exposure to passengers and crew. The airline industry requirements for space weather are currently in draft form with the United Nations International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). These draft requirements call for regional forecasts for navigation and communications impacts as well as radiation exposure predictions with advance warning of six, twelve, eighteen, and twenty-four hours. ICAO has not yet set the intensity thresholds for warning aviators of space weather storms, but these warnings will cover Global Positioning System-based navigation and radiation exposure at flight levels, in addition to the more common communications impacts.

Spacecraft/Satellite Operations

Geomagnetic storm impacts on spacecraft are mostly associated with enhancements in the radiation belts where geosynchronous spacecraft operate, though spacecraft in other orbits can be impacted. Spacecraft operators require forecasts one or more days in advance to enable preventative measures as well as to prepare recovery procedures.

Section III: Observations and Products Used for Geomagnetic Storm Forecasts

“NOAA is directed to submit a report to the Committee detailing: space weather data needs for operational forecasting”

Space weather geomagnetic storm forecasting depends on a number of ground- and space-based measurements. Each measurement plays a unique role at different phases of the forecasting process. These observations are separated into two groups: observations of the sun and observations of changes at or near Earth.

Images of the sun and its atmosphere (corona) are a primary input to the space weather forecasting process. The existence of sunspots and their size and complexity are the basic underpinnings of determining the likelihood and significance of a space weather event. Additionally, observations of the sun’s magnetic fields inform space weather models that can help forecast the propagation of an eruption from Sun to Earth.

The first sign of a solar eruption is typically the emission of light, characterized by the GOES spacecraft using the solar X-ray sensor and solar X-ray imager. The GOES-R Series replaces the solar X-ray imager with a solar EUV imager, providing better data on the sources of eruptions and the eruptions themselves. The primary benefit of these sensors is for predicting solar flares and solar radiation storms. These observations can provide an indication that an event has occurred along with a rough measure of the intensity and location of that event.

However, coronagraph imagery is required to determine whether or not part of the sun’s outer atmosphere – the corona – was explosively blown into space as part of the eruptive sequence (known as coronal mass ejections (CMEs)). The coronagraph imagery also is critical for determining the speed, size, and direction of the CME. A coronagraph anywhere on a straight line connecting the Sun and Earth, such as SOHO/LASCO is necessary for detecting Earth-directed CMEs and determining the parameters needed for forecasting. An additional coronagraph that has a side-on view of the Sun-Earth direction (such as from the Lagrange point 5 (L5), see image next page), can reduce the uncertainty in characterizing the speed, size, and direction of a CME. The NASA Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) mission provided such images between November 2009 and August 2010, when it passed through L5.

These coronagraph images feed physics-based models, such as the Wang-Sheeley-Arge (WSA) - Enlil model, that predict the arrival of a CME at Earth and, correspondingly, the commencement of a geomagnetic storm. In addition to coronagraph data to characterize the CME, the

GEOMAGNETIC STORM WATCHES ISSUED USING THE DATA (SOHO/LASCO & GONG) AND MODELS (WSA-ENLIL) DESCRIBED HERE SUPPORT THE 1-3 DAY USER ACTIONS PREVIOUSLY DESCRIBED

WSA-Enlil model requires solar magnetograph data, such as provided by the U.S. National Solar Observatory Global Oscillations Network Group (GONG). Applying the WSA-Enlil model, NOAA is able to issue the Geomagnetic Storm Watch product, which tells customers that a geomagnetic storm of a specified intensity is possible on a specified date. More detailed products, such as the 3-Day Geomagnetic Forecast, reflect a specific time of day the storm is

expected to commence, within a time window of three hours. However, the error bars from the model are more consistent with a window of ± 6 hours, so forecaster guidance is required to improve that number.

Lagrange Points in the Sun-Earth system (not to scale)

Very little new information is gathered from the time an eruption is observed at the sun until the environmental changes are recorded at the DSCOVR satellite, located in the solar wind at the Lagrange point 1 (L1) (see above image), roughly 15 minutes to one hour prior to impacting Earth.

Determination of the strength and orientation of the magnetic field within the CME must wait until it can be measured *in situ*. Orbital mechanics limit the practicality of where satellites may be positioned in orbit, so current state of the art is to capture the *in situ* properties of a CME at L1. This point is located approximately 1 million miles upstream (towards the sun) of Earth (a small fraction of the 93 million miles between the two bodies). These data show what Earth will experience in the following 15 to 60 minutes, with the exact time driven by the velocity of the CME. This information provides the basis for short-term warnings for geomagnetic storms and serves as the primary input for short-term forecasting models, such as the Geospace model, developed by the University of Michigan. The Geospace model, made operational in 2017, provides regional geomagnetic predictions for the first time ever.

GEOMAGNETIC STORM WARNINGS CANNOT MEET THE ELECTRIC POWER REQUIREMENT OF A FEW HOURS ADVANCE NOTICE NEEDED FOR BRINGING RESERVE OR MAINTENANCE POWER ON-LINE. DOING SO WOULD REQUIRE POSITIONING MONITORS CLOSER TO THE SUN, USING TECHNOLOGIES SUCH AS SOLAR SAILS. THE WARNINGS THAT ARE ISSUED DO ALLOW THE GRID TO REBALANCE LOADS, BUT DESENSITIZING PROTECTIVE RELAYS OR SHEDDING LOAD CURRENTLY REQUIRES MONITORING THE GRID ITSELF.

Additional lead time is available for the strongest events, when low energy (suprathermal) ions are detected at L1, such as with the Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor (EPAM) on the NASA Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) research mission. These suprathermal ions can be detected hours before the CME arrives at L1, giving information on the timing and intensity of the event.

After the detection of the event at L1, NOAA issues the Geomagnetic Storm Warning product with a lead time of fifteen minutes to one hour. This higher confidence product indicates that a geomagnetic storm of a specified intensity will begin imminently.

Lastly, ground-based measurements are important to characterizing the changes in the magnetic and electric fields at the surface of the earth, the driving physical phenomena behind the risk to the bulk electric power system. Ground-based magnetometers measure these changes and that data is combined with knowledge of the underlying geology, where characterized (*i.e.*, where magnetotelluric surveys have been completed), to describe the potential space weather impacts on the electrical power grid. Today, these do not provide a predictive product, but work is underway to incorporate magnetotelluric data into the Geospace model (in combination with additional modeling) to forecast the electric field as a function of location.

THE NEW GEOSPACE MODEL IS THE FIRST STEP TOWARDS PROVIDING POWER GRID OPERATORS WITH THE SPECIFIC INFORMATION THEY NEED ABOUT THE ENVIRONMENT AT THEIR OPERATING SITE.

Section IV: Known and Potential Gaps in Geomagnetic Storm Forecasting

“This report shall include... and shall identify any potential gaps in data needed for space weather forecasting.”

“NOAA is directed to submit a report to the Committee detailing: ...various options for attaining such data, cost estimates for those options, and corresponding timelines. The report shall also analyze the potential impact of a space weather data gap after 2019.”

This section details the highest priority expected gaps and potential gaps in data needed for geomagnetic storm forecasting. This includes gaps identified by NOAA’s partners where appropriate.

A. Coronagraph

The coronagraph is identified as a potential gap because the only Sun-Earth line coronagraph today is on the SOHO research spacecraft. This mission has a high risk of failure due to its age and the degradation of the solar panels. The SOHO mission launched in 1995 and had a lifetime expectancy of greater than 2 years with consumables for an extended period of time. Additionally, this science mission does not always provide timely observations due to the lack of dedicated and continuous ground-station tracking, a serious limitation on maximizing the lead time for significant events. NOAA has proposed the Space Weather Follow On (SWFO) mission to replace SOHO for operational coronagraph observations. This mission is not expected to be launched earlier than 2022.

Coronagraphs provide the only reliable way to observe and measure CME’s with the longest possible lead time. SWPC will not be able to meet the accuracy requirement of the Geomagnetic Storm Watch product for the electric power grid without coronagraph data.

Mitigation Strategies: The most effective mitigation against loss of the SOHO coronagraphs would be to accelerate the development of the Compact Coronagraph (CCOR) being developed for SWFO and to identify potential alternative locations for hosting a CCOR. NOAA released a Request for Information (RFI) on FedBizOpps (AB133E-16-RF-9999) in 2016 asking for other potential hosting options for CCOR. NOAA continues to explore the potential for hosting options with national or international partners.

B. Suprathermal Ions

Measurement of suprathermal ions is identified as a gap due to the likelihood of an interruption in the data stream. The current suprathermal ions measurements are provided by the aging Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE) mission, which was launched in 1997 and may fail before the SWFO mission launches. (Suprathermal ions were the highest priority solar wind observations that were not included on the DSCOVR spacecraft; however, suprathermal ions are a baseline measurement for the SWFO.)

These data aid in forecasting geomagnetic storms and in protecting assets in space. The information enables a more accurate Geomagnetic Storm Warning (for example, new products are planned that would improve the prediction of CME arrival time and geomagnetic storm intensity). Finally, some space assets, such as the NASA Chandra Advanced CCD Imaging Spectrometer, can be damaged by these protons, so observations of suprathermal ions allow the operators to take safety precautions.

Mitigation Strategies: Suprathermal ions can only be measured in interplanetary space. We are not aware of any planned missions that would launch prior to SWFO. Continued tracking of the NASA ACE mission in real-time is the only known mitigation strategy. NOAA is maintaining the capability to process the suprathermal ion data from ACE and make it available to customers. Global tracking stations are needed to downlink the data from ACE in real-time and provide that to NOAA.

C. Magnetotelluric Survey

Since 2006, the National Science Foundation has supported a national-scale magnetotelluric survey in the United States, through the EarthScope program, covering large geographic parts of the northwest, north-midwest, and southeast continental United States. In a separate, smaller project, USGS performed a magnetotelluric survey of the Florida peninsula in 2015. A survey of the northeast of the United States is underway at this time. By 2018, about two thirds of the Nation will have been surveyed, but there are presently no plans (nor is there any funding identified) to complete this survey for the other one third of the Nation.

Magnetotelluric data provide scientists with an estimate of the relationship between geomagnetic activity (such as during a storm) and the geo-electric field that is a hazard for the Nation's electric power grid. Thus, accurate forecasts of the impact to the electric power grid will not be possible for one third of the Nation.

Mitigation Strategies: Funding is required to complete the survey for the remaining third of the Nation. The cost of completing the magnetotelluric survey for the entire United States was estimated by USGS at \$5.5 million (over five years).

Section V: Inventory of NOAA and NOAA’s Partners Space Weather Assets

“This report shall include an inventory of all existing and planned space weather assets held by NOAA and NOAA's partners, to include each asset's function, operation and maintenance expenses, and lifetime cost estimates”

Deep Space

1) Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO)

Asset: SOHO

Agency: NASA

Status: Existing

Location: Lagrange point 1

Launch: 1995

Expected Lifetime: N/A

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 32,200 (includes \$30,000K in-kind per annum for Deep Space Network tracking/commanding/data downlink)

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 809,000

Instrument	Function
Large Angle Spectrometric Coronagraph (LASCO)	LASCO provides imagery and characterization of CMEs that are the basis for estimating their direction and velocity. These are the primary inputs into CME forecast models and the resulting geomagnetic storm forecasts. Currently, there are sizable daily gaps in near real-time data availability due to funding for tracking time and other mission prioritizations.

2) Advanced Composition Explorer (ACE)

Asset: ACE

Agency: NASA

Status: Existing

Location: Lagrange point 1

Launch: 1997

Expected Lifetime: N/A

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 6,500*

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 325,000

* including \$3,500K per year for Deep Space Network tracking/commanding/data downlink

Instruments	Function
Magnetometer (MAG)	MAG measures the interplanetary magnetic field upstream of Earth. Provides data that enable highly accurate warnings of geomagnetic

	storms and are used as input to models to forecast the state of the magnetosphere and ionosphere. Warning times of up to 1 hour are possible.
Solar Wind Electron Proton Alpha Monitor (SWEPAM)	SWEPAM measures the interplanetary solar wind upstream of Earth. Provides data that enable highly accurate warnings of geomagnetic storms and are used as input to models to forecast the state of the magnetosphere and ionosphere. Warning times of up to 1 hour are possible.
Electron, Proton, and Alpha Monitor (EPAM)	EPAM measures the flux and direction of electrons above 30 keV, ions greater than 50 keV and the elemental composition of the ions in the solar wind upstream from Earth. It provides an indication of geomagnetic storm intensity, minutes and sometimes hours before the shock arrival at the spacecraft, and subsequently, Earth.
Solar Isotope Spectrometer (SIS)	SIS measures the flux of both galactic cosmic rays and solar energetic particles. Both measurements are applicable to characterizing satellite hazards and assessing spaceflight and aviation radiation hazards.

3) Deep Space Climate Observatory (DSCOVR)

Asset: DSCOVR

Agency: NOAA as an on-orbit asset

Status: Existing

Location: Lagrange point 1

Launch: 2015

Expected Lifetime: FY 2015 – FY 2020 (estimated)

Formulation and Development (Triana): NASA: FY 1998 – FY 2003

Refurbishment (DSCOVR): NOAA: FY 2011 – FY 2016

Operations and Maintenance period: NOAA: FY 2016 – present

Asset Function: DSCOVR provides the nation's real-time solar wind monitoring capabilities from deep space.

Potential Gaps: Possible gap between the end of DSCOVR mission life and the on-orbit deployment of SWFO.

NOAA Budget (Based on FY 2018 President's Budget Request, FY 2017 Operational Phase Transfer, and FY 2016 reprogramming).

- Life Cycle Cost: \$136.2 million (refurbishment cost of primary NOAA instrument, the Plasma Magnetometer, was \$1.8 million)
- Satellite Operations and Maintenance: \$27.3 million

NASA Budget

- Value of DSCOVR satellite as transferred to NOAA (November 2015 timeframe): \$216 million. Dollars not adjusted for inflation.

Air Force Budget

- Launch services: ~\$165.0 million

Assumptions used to develop the budgets: Budgets below represent a hybrid of original NASA development costs, NOAA funding to refurbish the space weather instruments, and

U.S. Air Force launch services. Costs do not include NASA costs to refurbish the two Earth-pointing instruments, EPIC and NISTAR.

Instrument	Function
Plasma Magnetometer (PlasmaMag)	<p>The PlasmaMag measures solar wind for space weather predictions consists of three instruments:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The magnetometer measures the interplanetary magnetic field upstream of Earth. Providing data that enables highly accurate warnings of geomagnetic storms and used as input to models to forecast the state of the magnetosphere and ionosphere. Warning times of up to 1 hour are possible. 2) The Faraday cup measures the interplanetary solar wind upstream of Earth. Providing data that enables highly accurate warnings of geomagnetic storms and used as input to models to forecast the state of the magnetosphere and ionosphere. Warning times of up to 1 hour are possible. 3) The electrostatic analyzer measures the interplanetary solar wind upstream of Earth. Providing data that complements the Faraday Cup, by allowing higher speed solar wind to be measured. Warning times of up to 1 hour are possible.

4) Space Weather Follow On (SWFO)

Asset: SWFO

Agency: NOAA

Status: Planned

Location: Lagrange point 1

Launch: TBD - no earlier than FY 2022

Expected Lifetime: TBD

Formulation: FY 2016 – FY 2017

Development: FY 2018 – at least FY 2022

Operations and Maintenance period: Not earlier than FY 2022 – FY 2032

Asset Function: SWFO will provide continuity for solar wind and CME measurements. The first instrument, to measure solar wind (PLAS/MAG/ION), will provide operational continuity to DSCOVR, which will reach the end of its mission design life in FY 2022. This instrument will also add the suprathermal ion measurement. The second instrument, the CCOR for CME, will provide continuity to the NASA research mission, SOHO, which has exceeded its design life.

Potential Gaps: Likely gap in CME imagery between the SOHO/LASCO end of life and the start of the SWFO program. There is a possible gap for solar wind data between the end of DSCOVR’s mission life and the launch of the SWFO.

Budget (based on FY 2018 President’s Budget request): FY 2018 President Budget request is \$500K

Assumptions used to develop the budgets: The SWFO mission is in the pre-formulation phase. Current cost estimates are based on formal Requests for Information and initial analyses and is being refined in FY 2017. As part of this process, NOAA continues to

explore other national and international partnership opportunities for hosting of payloads and meeting the needs for SWFO.

Instruments	Estimated Development Cost	Function
Solar Wind (PLAS/MAG/ION) instrument 2 sets	\$91M	To provide <i>in situ</i> , Earth-directed solar wind measurements in near real time allowing 15-60 minute warnings of geomagnetic storm conditions. (Cost is as delivered. Includes project management, systems engineering, mission assurance, integration and testing, and reserves)
CCOR for CME imagery 2 units	\$47M	To provide imagery of CMEs to provide 1-4 day warnings of geomagnetic storm conditions. (Cost is as delivered. Includes project management, systems engineering, mission assurance, integration and testing, and reserves)

Geosynchronous Orbit

1) Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites – N Series (GOES-N Series)

Asset: GOES-N Series (GOES-N/O/P)

Agency: NOAA

Status: Existing

Location: Geostationary orbit

Launch: GOES-N (GOES-13) – 2006; GOES-O (GOES-14) – 2009; GOES-N (GOES-15) – 2010

Expected Operational Lifetime: FY 2006 – present

Formulation and Development period: FY 1998 - FY 2011

Operations and Maintenance period: FY 2006 - present

Asset Function: The GOES-N Series is the Nation’s operational geostationary weather satellites. The satellites provide imaging and sounding measurements that support weather forecasts and monitoring of solar activity. The GOES-N Series is a three-satellite program (GOES-N/O/P) that was developed using technology from the GOES I-M Series through a fixed price contract with Boeing Space Systems.

Potential Gaps: None.

Budget (Based on FY 2018 President’s Budget Request)

- Life Cycle Cost: \$2.296 billion.
- Formulation and Development Cost: \$1.854 billion
- Satellite Operations and Maintenance: \$ 0.442 billion

Assumptions used to develop the budgets: GOES-N Series was acquired as a fixed price contract to make almost identical copies of the GOES-I-M Series. The GOES-N Series flies both meteorological and space weather instruments and includes formulation, development,

launch, and program management for three satellites. The cost for the entire mission is presented since it is impossible to provide separate space weather from other mission costs.

Instruments	Development Cost	Function
Solar X-ray Imager (3 units)	\$99.1M	Solar X-ray Imager monitors the sun's X-rays for the early detection of solar flares and other phenomena. It provides images the inner corona of the sun to provide locations and morphologies of flares, coronal holes and active regions. These contribute to forecasts of solar flares, geomagnetic storms, and solar energetic particle events.
SEM for GOES NOP (3 units)	\$106.0M	<p>SEM consists of three instrument groups: 1) an energetic particle sensor (EPS) package, 2) two magnetometer sensors, and 3) a solar X-ray sensor (XRS).</p> <p>The EPS measures energetic particles, including electrons, protons, and alpha particles. The energetic particle environment impacts satellites, launch operations, aircraft electronics, astronauts, airline passengers, and high-latitude radio communication. Data are required to issue forecasts, warnings, and alerts of hazardous conditions.</p> <p>The magnetometer provides measurements of the magnetic field that controls charged particle motion that impacts satellites launch operations, aircraft electronics, astronauts, airline passengers, and high-latitude radio communication. Data are required for validation of Geospace models that are used to predict geomagnetic activity, to support sounding rocket launch decisions, to monitor the location of Earth's magnetopause, to alert customers to solar wind shocks and sudden impulses, and to assess changes in Earth's space environment.</p> <p>The XRS provides absolute measure of solar flare magnitude. Provides key input for one of the three NOAA Space Weather Scales. Drives models of HF radio wave propagation and absorption. Solar flares are the precursor to nearly every major space weather storm. The size of the storm and the magnitude of the impacts are closely correlated to the size of the solar flare. There is also an EUVS that is a part of this instrument. It provides absolute measure of solar extreme ultraviolet irradiance. Drives models of the ionosphere and thermosphere that support radio communication, satellite navigation, and satellite drag (collision avoidance).</p>

2) Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO)

Asset: SDO

Agency: NASA

Status: Existing

Location: Geosynchronous orbit

Launch: 2010

Expected Lifetime: N/A

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 12,000

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 981,000

Instruments	Function
Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA)	AIA images the inner corona of the sun to provide locations and morphologies of flares, coronal holes and active regions. These contribute to forecasts of solar flares, geomagnetic storms, and solar energetic particle events.
Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI)	HMI high cadence data depicts the morphology, dynamics and evolution of sunspot regions and their corresponding magnetic fields on the near side of the sun. These data inform probabilistic forecasts for flares and energetic proton events. Far-side helioseismology provides advanced indication of new or returning active regions and informs probabilistic forecasts as described above as well as 10.7 cm solar flux deterministic forecasts.
Extreme ultraviolet Variability Experiment (EVE)	EVE provides absolute measure of solar extreme ultraviolet irradiance. Drives models of the ionosphere and thermosphere that support radio communication, satellite navigation, and satellite drag (collision avoidance). Provides a proxy (i.e., backup) for the GOES X-Ray Sensor (XRS).

3) Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites - R Series (GOES-R Series)

Asset: GOES-R Series (GOES-R/S/T/U)

Agency: NOAA

Status: Existing (GOES-R) and in development (GOES-S/T/U)

Location: Geostationary orbit

Launch: GOES-R (now GOES-16) in 2016; GOES-S planned FY 2018; GOES-T planned FY 2020; GOES-U planned FY 2025

Expected Series Lifetime: FY 2017 - FY 2036

Formulation and Development period: FY 2000 - FY 2025

Operations and Maintenance period: FY 2017 - FY 2036

Asset Function: The GOES-R Series is the Nation's next generation of geostationary weather satellites. GOES-R (GOES-16) was launched in 2016 and will go operational late in 2017. The satellites will provide advanced imaging with increased spatial resolution and faster coverage for more accurate forecasts, real-time mapping of lightning activity, and improved monitoring of solar activity. The GOES-R Series is a four-satellite program

(GOES-R/S/T/U) that will extend the availability of the operational GOES satellite system through 2036.

Potential Gaps: None known between now and end of the program (FY 2036).

Budget (Based on FY 2018 President’s Budget request and FY 2017 Operational Phase Transfer) ²

- Life Cycle Cost: \$10.828 billion
- Formulation and Development Cost: \$10.150 billion
- Satellite Operations and Maintenance: \$0.678 billion

Assumptions used to develop the budgets: GOES-R Series hosts both meteorological and space weather instruments and includes formulation, development, launch, and program management for four satellites. The cost for the entire mission is presented since it is impossible to provide separate space weather costs from other mission costs.

Instruments	Cost	Function
Extreme Ultraviolet (EUV) and X-ray Irradiance Sensors (EXIS) (4 units)	\$103.8M	<p>EXIS consists of two main sensors, the Extreme Ultraviolet Sensor (EUVS) and the X-Ray Sensor (XRS).</p> <p>XRS provides absolute measure of solar flare magnitude. Provides key input for one of the three NOAA Space Weather Scales. Drives models of HF radio wave propagation and absorption. Solar flares are the precursor to nearly every major space weather storm. The size of the storm and the magnitude of the impacts are closely correlated to the size of the solar flare.</p> <p>EUVS provides absolute measure of solar extreme ultraviolet irradiance. Drives models of the ionosphere and thermosphere that support radio communication, satellite navigation, and satellite drag (collision avoidance).</p>
Solar Ultraviolet Imager (SUVI) (4 units)	\$292.0M	<p>SUVI will observe and characterize complex active regions of the sun, solar flares, and the eruptions of solar filaments that may give rise to CMEs. SUVI replaces the current GOES-NOP Solar X-ray Imager (SXI) instrument and represents a change in both spectral coverage and spatial resolution over SXI. These contribute to forecasts of solar flares, geomagnetic storms, and solar energetic particle events.</p>

² Development, launch, ground system, long-term archive, and program management of four satellites through FY 2036.

Space Environment In-Situ Suite (SEISS) ² (4 units)	\$127.3M	SEISS is comprised of four sensors that will monitor proton, electron, and heavy ion fluxes in the magnetosphere. Data from SEISS will drive solar radiation storm portion of NOAA space weather scales and other alerts and warnings and will improve energetic particle forecasts.
Magnetometer (MAG) ² (4 units)	\$10.6M	MAG provides measurements of the magnetic field that controls charged particle motion that impacts satellites launch operations, aircraft electronics, astronauts, airline passengers, and high-latitude radio communication. Data are required for validation of Geospace models that are used to predict geomagnetic activity, to support sounding rocket launch decisions, to monitor the location of Earth's magnetopause, to alert customers to solar wind shocks and sudden impulses, and to assess changes in Earth's space environment.

4) Global-scale Observations of the Limb and Disk (GOLD)

Asset: GOLD

Agency: NASA

Status: Planned

Location: Geostationary orbit

Launch: TBD – planned 2017

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 2,700

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 33,400

Instruments	Function
Ultraviolet Imaging Spectrograph	Measures temperature and composition in the upper atmosphere. Will be used to drive models of the ionosphere and thermosphere for radio communication, satellite navigation, and satellite drag (collision avoidance).

Polar Orbit

1) Polar Operational Environmental Satellites (POES)

Asset: POES (NOAA K/L/M/N/N Prime)

Agency: NOAA

Status: Existing

Location: Low earth orbit

Launch: NOAA K (NOAA-15) – 1998; NOAA L (NOAA-16) – 2000; NOAA M (NOAA-17) – 2002; NOAA N (NOAA-18) – 2005; NOAA N Prime (NOAA-19) - 2009

Expected Operational Lifetime: FY 1998 – present

Formulation and Development period: FY 1986 – FY 2009

Operations and Maintenance period: NOAA: FY 1998 – present

Asset Function: The POES satellite system offers the advantage of daily global coverage, by making nearly polar orbits fourteen times per day. Data from the POES series supports a broad range of environmental monitoring applications including weather analysis and forecasting, climate research and prediction, global sea surface temperature measurements, atmospheric soundings of temperature and humidity, ocean dynamics research, volcanic eruption monitoring, forest fire detection, global vegetation analysis, search and rescue, and many other applications.

Potential Gaps: End of the polar-orbit Space Environment Monitor (SEM) measurements when the last POES satellite ceases to provide useful data. There are no space weather instruments on successor polar-orbiting satellite programs.

NOAA Budget (Based on FY 2018 President’s Budget Request)

- Life Cycle Cost: \$2.569 billion.
- Formulation and Development Cost: \$2.108 billion
- Satellite Operations and Maintenance: \$0.461 billion

Assumptions used to develop the budgets: NOAA K-N Prime Series flies both meteorological and space weather instruments, and includes formulation, development, launch, and program management for five satellites. The cost for the entire mission is presented since it is impossible to separate the space weather component from other mission costs.

Instruments	Development Cost	Function
SEM-2 (5 units)	\$29.48M	SEM measurements of Earth's radiation belts and charged particle fluxes at satellite altitude. Provides charged particle measurements used to characterize the auroral zone and polar cap. Supports satellite operations and spacecraft anomaly resolution.

2) Meteorological Operational (Metop)

Asset: Metop

Agency: EUMETSAT (four NOAA-provided instruments flown on Metop-A, four NOAA-provided instruments on Metop-B, and three NOAA-provided instruments on Metop-C)

Status: Existing and in development

Location: Low earth orbit

Launch: Metop-A – 2006; Metop-B – 2012; Metop-C planned 2018

NOAA Budget (Based on FY 2018 President’s Budget request)

- Life Cycle Cost: \$372.925 million. NOAA dollars only for instrument cost and on-orbit support.
- Formulation and Development Cost: N/A (included in NOAA K-N Prime budget)
- Satellite Operations and Maintenance: EUMETSAT supports satellite operations and maintenance. NOAA provides \$46.1 million for on-orbit anomaly support for NOAA-provided instruments.

Instrument	Function
Space Environment Monitor	Charged particle measurements originally used to characterize the auroral zone and polar cap. Currently used to support satellite operations and spacecraft anomaly resolution.

3) Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP)

Asset: DMSP

Agency: Department of Defense

Status: Existing

Location: Low earth orbit

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): Unknown

Lifetime Costs (\$K): Unknown

Instruments	Function
Multiple	A constellation of satellites that each carries a suite of space weather sensors. These sensors detect auroral emissions and other ionospheric parameters that are then used in space weather models and applications.

Heliocentric Orbit

1) Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO)

Asset: STEREO

Agency: NASA

Status: Existing

Location: Heliocentric orbit

Launch: 2006

Expected Lifetime: N/A

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 43,300*

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 695,000

* including \$35,000k in-kind per annum for Deep Space Network tracking/commanding/data downlink

Instruments	Function
Sun Earth Connections Coronal and Heliospheric Investigation (SECCHI)	SECCHI has four instruments: an extreme ultraviolet imager, two white-light coronagraphs, and a heliospheric imager. These instruments study the 3-D evolution of CME's from birth at the sun's surface through the corona and interplanetary medium to its eventual impact at Earth. When in a useable position, the coronagraph data enable more accurate parameterization and modeling of CME's and the differential diagnosis of geoeffective (i.e., storm inducing) versus non-geoeffective CME's. The heliospheric imager permits tracking of the CME through the heliosphere and can be used for operational analysis and validation of model solutions.
Plasma and Suprathermal	PLASTIC samples the solar wind and suprathermal particles, providing measurements of kinetic properties and composition. It provides forecasters

Ion Composition (PLASTIC)	with insight into the solar wind characteristics of co-rotating structures before they arrive at Earth.
<i>In situ</i> Measurements of Particles and CME Transients (IMPACT)	IMPACT is a suite of seven instruments that samples the 3-D distribution of solar wind plasma electrons, the characteristics of the solar energetic particle (SEP) ions and electrons, and the local vector magnetic field. This instrument provides forecasters with insight into the solar wind characteristics of co-rotating structures before they arrive at Earth.

Equatorial Orbit

1) Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate (COSMIC)

Asset: COSMIC-2A

Agency: Multiple (Taiwan, NOAA, U.S. Air Force)

Status: Existing

Location: Equatorial orbit

Launch: TBD – no earlier than FY 2018

Expected Operational Lifetime: FY 2018 – FY 2023 (or end of spacecraft life)

Formulation: 2011-2014

Development: 2014-2018

Operations and Maintenance Period: 2018-2023 (estimated)

Asset Function: Satellite radio occultation measurements provide a measure of the number of electrons between the radio occultation satellite and the GPS satellite. When combined with ground-based observations of the horizontal structure of the ionosphere, it is possible to create a three-dimensional reconstruction of the ionosphere needed to specify the transmission and reflection characteristics of the ionosphere for radio communication, satellite navigation (GPS), and satellite communication.

Potential Gaps: Gap in radio occultation likely between COSMIC-1 and deployment of replacement polar-orbiting satellites. Launched in 2006 and now well past their five-year design life, only one of the original six COSMIC-1 satellites remains operational.

Budget (Based on FY 2018 President’s Budget Request)

- Life Cycle Cost (estimated): \$33.86M

Assumptions used to develop the budgets: Taiwan, NASA, and the U.S. Air Force have borne the majority of the satellite development and launch costs. NOAA has focused on the ground system development. COSMIC-2A will provide technological improvements over COSMIC-1.

Contribution	Partner	Funding (\$M)
Instruments	U.S. Air Force	Funding provided by USAF
Launch services	U.S. Air Force	Funding provided by USAF
Ground System	NOAA/NESDIS	\$33.86M

(Data Processing System and Ground Site Antennas)		
Ground system	U.S. Air Force (Mark IV-B)	Funding provided by USAF
Spacecraft bus	Taiwan/NSPO/ Orbital Sciences	Funding provided by Taiwan/NSPO

Radiation Belts

1) Van Allen Probes (VAP)

Asset: VAP

Agency: NASA

Status: Existing

Location: Radiation Belts

Launch: 2012

Expected Lifetime: 2019

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 12,000

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 981,000

Instruments	Function
Magnetic Electron Ion Spectrometer (MagEIS)	MagEIS measures energetic electrons and ions in the Earth's magnetosphere, as part of the larger Energetic Particle, Composition, and Thermal Plasma Suite. These data inform models that allow forecasters and spacecraft operators to assess the temporal and spatial changes in the radiation belts.

Ground

1) Ionosondes

Asset: Ionosondes

Agency: Various

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 1,400 (50 per site for 28 sites)

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 23,800 (850 per site for 28 sites)

Instruments	Function
Ionosonde	Provides detailed height resolved electron density profiles of the lower ionosphere. These observations are essential to assessing the lower ionosphere structure that blocks or absorbs radio communication. Ionosonde data are assimilated into regional and global models of the ionosphere.

2) GPS Receivers

Asset: GPS Receivers

Agency: Various

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 1,000 (10 per site for 100 sites)

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 15,000 (150 per site for 100 sites for 10 years)

Instruments	Function
GPS Receiver	Provides estimates of the ionosphere induced errors and the availability of the GPS system. Measurements of the calculated positions of GPS receivers at fixed locations provide an estimate of the positioning error for at any given site. The line of sight signal delays for each satellite provide an estimate of the number of ionospheric electrons between the ground receiver and the satellite transmitter. This information provides a map of the horizontal structure of the ionosphere. When combined with the vertical profiles obtained from the COSMIC-2 satellite occultation data, it is possible to create the three-dimensional reconstruction of the ionosphere needed to specify the transmission and reflection characteristics of the ionosphere for radio communication, satellite navigation (GPS), and satellite communication.

3) Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG)

Asset: GONG

Agency: NSF

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 1000

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 47,000

Instruments	Function
Global Oscillation Network Group (GONG)	GONG consists of six sites situated around the Earth to provide near continuous observations of the sun. GONG data consists of H-alpha images, which are used to detect and characterize solar flares and eruptive filaments; magnetograms, which are used to characterize the magnetic structure of active regions and as input to operational models of solar wind expansion such as WSA-Enlil; and helioseismology measurements, which provide information about active regions on the far side of the sun. Starting in FY 2016 NOAA began funding the O&M costs of the six GONG sites as well as began the transition of the operational processing and archiving of these data onto its operational computing infrastructure.

4) Neutron Monitors

Asset: Neutron Monitors

Agency: NSF

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 300

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 6,750 (Cost to build, not including real-estate, is 750/station. Lifetime costs assume 20 years of operation.)

Instruments	Function
Neutron Monitor	Neutron monitors provide information on background galactic cosmic ray intensities (but not composition), and additionally, provide valuable input on the energy spectrum of solar radiation events. These measurements, distributed across a number of latitudes, can help characterize the aviation radiation environment during a significant space weather event.

5) Solar Optical Observing Network (SOON)

Asset: SOON

Agency: Department of Defense

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (Learmonth, Australia; Holloman AFB, New Mexico; San Vito, Italy)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): Unknown

Lifetime Costs (\$K): Unknown

Instruments	Function
Solar Optical Observing Network (SOON)	The U.S. Air Force SOON is a network of three ground based telescopes. These telescopes provide near continuous monitoring in the H-Alpha and white light wavelengths from the sun. Sunspot and active region analysis are carried out by personnel at these locations and the data is sent to both the US Air Force Space weather operations center as well as the SWPC forecast office. Furthermore, these observatories detect optical flares in near real-time and are used as a proxy for solar X-ray flares that can have significant impacts on both civilian and military operations.

6) Radio Solar Telescope Network (RSTN)

Asset: RSTN

Agency: DoD

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (Sagamore Hill, Massachusetts; Kaena Point, Hawaii; San Vito, Italy; Learmonth, Australia)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): Unknown

Lifetime Costs (\$K): Unknown

Instruments	Function
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Radio Solar Telescope Network (RSTN)	These USAF radio telescopes monitor eight discrete frequencies ranging from 245 MHz to 15400 MHz as well as monitor the continuous spectrum from 25 MHz to 180 MHz. The primary function of these telescopes is to detect radio emissions from the sun to include significant radio bursts and radio sweeps that impact both military and civilian communications and operations.
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7) NEXt generation IOnosonde Network (NEXION)

Asset: NEXION

Agency: Department of Defense

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (Various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): Unknown

Lifetime Costs (\$K): Unknown

Instruments	Function
Ionosondes	NEXION is the USAF Next Generation Ionosonde network and is comprised of nine sites globally. These ionosondes provide ionospheric data and information that is used in military space weather models and applications.

8) Ionospheric Scintillation TEC Observer network (ISTO)

Asset: ISTO

Agency: Department of Defense

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (Various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): Unknown

Lifetime Costs (\$K): Unknown

Instruments	Function
GPS Receiver	This network is composed of six sites globally that are located in the near equatorial regions to detect ionospheric scintillation. Data and information from the ISTO network is used in space weather models and applications that directly impact military operations.

9) Magnetometers

Asset: Magnetometers

Agency: USGS

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 175* (per observatory)

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 9,000** (per observatory)

*Six observatories in the lower 48 states, five additional over N. America, two additional in

the Pacific

**Does not include the cost of the land, which is highly variable

Instruments	Function
Magnetometers	Magnetometers provide highly-reliable, real-time measurements of Earth's time-varying magnetic field. The data are required to specify the level of geomagnetic activity. The data are combined with identical observations from international partners to derive the NOAA G-scale, a global indicator of activity that NOAA forecasts and uses to issue watches, warnings, and alerts. A significant portion of NOAA/ SWPC users are adversely affected by geomagnetic activity, including the electrical power industry, spacecraft operations, GPS users, pipelines, and radio communication.

Asset: Magnetometers

Agency: International (various)

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (various)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): 175 per observatory

Lifetime Costs (\$K): 9,000* (per observatory)

*Does not include the cost of the land, which is highly variable

Instruments	Function
Magnetometers	Magnetometers provide highly-reliable, real-time measurements of Earth's time-varying magnetic field. The data are required to specify the level of geomagnetic activity. The data are combined with identical observations from international partners to derive the NOAA G-scale, a global indicator of activity that NOAA forecasts and uses to issue watches, warnings, and alerts. A significant portion of NOAA/ SWPC users are adversely affected by geomagnetic activity, including the electrical power industry, spacecraft operations, GPS users, pipelines, and radio communication.

10) Dominion Radio Astrophysical Observatory (DRAO)

Asset: DRAO

Agency: Natural Resources Canada

Status: Existing

Location: Ground (British Columbia, Canada)

Annual O&M Costs (\$K): Unknown

Lifetime Costs (\$K): Unknown

Instruments	Function
Dominion Radio Astrophysical Observatory (DRAO)	DRAO observes F10.7 radio flux, a measure of the noise level generated by the sun at a wavelength of 10.7 cm. This index is an input to ionospheric models as a surrogate for the solar output in wavelengths that produce photoionization in the Earth's ionosphere (in the ultraviolet bands). It is routinely used as input into high frequency (3-30 MHz) radio propagation

	models.
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